
Supplementary Material for the publication “A data science and historical international political ecology perspective on the financial system, agriculture and climate: from the trans-Atlantic slave trade to agroecology”

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Visualisations and code

S1 interactive timelines and events chart. *The dynamic chart from which the figure element Fig 1 was created.* The HTML file was generated using S1 code.

- `S1_English_British_population_and_English_British_agricultural_crops.html` (HTML file: visualisation)
- `English_British_population_and_English_British_agricultural_crops.eps` (EPS file: figure element)

S1 code. *The R script used to generate S1 interactive timelines and events chart and the input datasets.*

- `S1_Population_vs_Crop.R` (TEXT file: R code)
- Population data
- Crop data
- British colonialism-related data

S2 interactive timelines and events chart. *The dynamic chart from which the figure element of Fig 2 was created.* The HTML file was generated using S2 code.

- `S2_English_British_population_and_English_British_agricultural_livestock.html` (HTML file: visualisation)
- `English_British_population_and_English_British_agricultural_livestock.eps` (EPS file: figure element)

S2 code. *The R script used to generate S2 interactive timelines and events chart and the input datasets.*

- `S2_Population_vs_Livestock.R` (TEXT file: R code)
- Population data
- Livestock data
- British colonialism-related data

S3 interactive timelines and events chart. *The dynamic chart from which the figure element of Fig 3 was created.* The HTML file was generated using S3 code.

- `S3_English_British_population_and_English_British_industrial.html` (HTML file: visualisation)
- `English_British_population_and_English_British_industrial.eps` (EPS file: figure element)

S3 code. *The R script used to generate S3 interactive timelines and events chart and input datasets.*

- `S3_Population_vs_Industrial.R` (TEXT file: R code)
- Population data
- Industrial data
- British colonialism-related data

S4 interactive timelines and events chart. *The dynamic chart from which the figure element of Fig 4 was created.* The HTML file was generated using S4 code.

- `S4_English_British_population_and_English_British_GDP0.html` (HTML file: visualisation)
- `English_British_population_and_English_British_GDP0.eps` (EPS file: figure element)

S4 code. *The R script used to generate S4 interactive timelines and events chart and input datasets.*

- `S4_Population_vs_GDP.R` (TEXT file: R code)
- Population data
- GDP(O) data
- British colonialism-related data

S5 interactive timelines and events chart. *The dynamic chart from which the figure element of Fig 5 was created.* The HTML file was generated using S5 code.

- `S5_English_British_population_and_regional_trade.html` (HTML file: visualisation)
- `English_British_population_and_regional_trade.eps` (EPS file: figure element)

S5 code. *The R script used to generate S5 interactive timelines and events chart and input datasets.*

- `S5_Population_vs_Exports_Imports.R` (TEXT file: R code)
- Population data
- Trade data
- British colonialism-related data

S6 interactive timelines and events chart. *The dynamic chart from which the figure element of Fig 6 was created.* The HTML file was generated using S6 code.

- `S6_Number_captives_transportated_and_English_British_agricultural_crops.html` (HTML file: visualisation)
- `Number_captives_transportated_and_English_British_agricultural_crops.eps` (EPS file: figure element)

S6 code. *The R script used to generate S6 interactive timelines and events chart and input datasets.*

- `S6_Slaves_vs_Crop.R` (TEXT file: R code)
- Slave-related data
- Crop data
- British colonialism-related data

S7 interactive timelines and events chart. *The dynamic chart from which the figure element of Fig 7 was created.* The HTML file was generated using S7 code.

- `S7_Number_captives_transportated_and_English_British_agricultural_livestock.html` (HTML file: visualisation)
- `Number_captives_transportated_and_English_British_agricultural_livestock.eps` (EPS file: figure element)

S7 code. *The R script used to generate S7 interactive timelines and events chart and input datasets.*

- `S7_Slaves_vs_Livestock.R` (TEXT file: R code)
- Slave-related data
- Livestock data
- British colonialism-related data

S8 interactive timelines and events chart. *The dynamic chart from which the figure element of Fig 8 was created.* The HTML file was generated using S8 code.

- `S8_Number_captives_transportated_and_English_British_industrial.html` (HTML file: visualisation)
- `Number_captives_transportated_and_English_British_industrial.eps` (EPS file: figure element)

S8 code. *The R script used to generate S8 interactive timelines and events chart and input datasets.*

- `S8_Slaves_vs_Industrial.R` (TEXT file: R code)
- Slave-related data
- Industrial data
- British colonialism-related data

S9 interactive timelines and events chart. *The dynamic chart from which the figure element of Fig 9 was created.* The HTML file was generated using S9 code.

- S9_Number_captives_transportated_and_English_British_GDP0.html (HTML file: visualisation)
- Number_captives_transportated_and_English_British_GDP0.eps (EPS file: figure element)

S9 code. *The R script used to generate S9 interactive timelines and events chart and input datasets.*

- S9_Slaves_vs_GDP.R (TEXT file: R code)
- Slave-related data
- GDP(O) data
- British colonialism-related data

S10 interactive timelines and events chart. *The dynamic chart from which the figure element of Fig 10 was created.* The HTML file was generated using S10 code.

- S10_Number_captives_transportated_and_regional_trade.html (HTML file: visualisation)
- Number_captives_transportated_and_regional_trade.eps (EPS file: figure element)

S10 code. *The R script used to generate S10 interactive timelines and events chart and input datasets.*

- S10_Slaves_vs_GDP.R (TEXT file: R code)
- Slave-related data
- Trade data
- British colonialism-related data

S11 interactive cartogram. *The dynamic cartogram from which the figure element of Fig 11 was created.* The HTML file was generated using S11 code.

- S11_Colonies_slave_map.html (HTML file: visualisation)
- Colonies_slave_map.eps (EPS file: figure element)

S11 code. *The R script used to generate S11 interactive cartogram and input datasets.*

- S11_Slaves_vs_GDP.R (TEXT file: R code)
- Slave-related data
- European colonialism-related data

S12 interactive timelines and events chart. *The dynamic chart from which the figure element of Fig 12 was created.* The HTML file was generated using S12 code.

- S12_Central_bank_interest_rates_agricultural_production_targets_land_acquisition.html (HTML file: visualisation)
- Central_bank_interest_rates_agricultural_production_targets_land_acquisition.eps (EPS file: figure element)

S12 code. *The R script used to generate S12 interactive timelines and events chart and input datasets.*

- S12_US_UK_int_rates_kyle_trade_agreements.R (TEXT file: R code)
- UK interest rates
- USA interest rates
- Agricultural production and global land acquisitions
- Historical and operative trade agreements

S13 interactive cartogram. *The dynamic cartogram from which the figure element of Fig 13 was created.*
The HTML file was generated using S13 code.

- S13_landgrab_map.html (HTML file: visualisation)
- landgrab_map.eps (EPS file: figure element)

S13 code. *The R script used to generate S13 interactive cartogram and input datasets.*

- S13_landgrab_map.R (TEXT file: R code)
- Global land acquisitions
- Global land acquisitions and UK/USA investors
- Impact of synthetic biology on natural products

S14 timelines and events chart. *The dynamic chart from which the figure element of Fig 14 was created.*
The HTML file was generated using S14 code.

- S14_Average_global_oxygen_carbon_dioxide_and_ElNino_ElNina.html (HTML file: visualisation)
- Average_global_oxygen_carbon_dioxide_and_ElNino_ElNina.eps (EPS file: figure element)

S14 code. *The R script used to generate S14 timelines and events chart and input datasets.*

- S14_Average_global_oxygen_carbon_dioxide_and_ElNino_ElNina.R (TEXT file: R code)
- Global O₂ levels
- Global CO₂ levels
- El Niño and La Niña episodes

S15 interactive cartogram. *The dynamic cartogram from which the figure element of Fig 15 was created.*
The HTML file was generated using S15 code.

- S15_agro_map.html (HTML file: visualisation))
- agro_map.eps (EPS file: figure element)
- blackwheat.png (PNG file: icon)
- SBLogo.png (PNG file: icon)
- Synthetic_Biology_Logo.png (PNG file: icon)

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- `uk_flag2.png` (PNG file: icon)
 - `us_flag2.png` (PNG file: icon)
 - `wff_transp.png` (PNG file: icon)
 - `wheat_icon.png` (PNG file: icon)

S15 code. *The R script used to generate S15 interactive cartogram and input datasets.*

- `S15_agro_map.R` (TEXT file: R code)
- La Via Campesina (LVC)
- World Forum of Fish Harvesters and Fish Workers (WFF)
- Globally Important Agricultural Heritage Systems (GIAHS) data
- Centres of agricultural biodiversity

Original resource(s) and datasets

Bank of England historical macroeconomic data. *A broad set of macroeconomic and financial data for the UK stretching back in some cases to the 13th century and 1086, the year of the Domesday Book released by the Bank of England.*

The original (re)source is

Research datasets: A millennium of macroeconomic data

This file is version 3 of the dataset; selected Sheets/Tables/Columns were used to create various input datasets
`millenniumofdata_v3_final.xlsx` (XLS file: spreadsheet)

Population data. *Population of England (1086 – 1870) and Great Britain (1700 – 1870).* This quantity is a proxy for the internal workforce; the values listed are overestimates of this labour force because the numbers include more than working age individuals.

Sheet A2 (English and British population (millions)) of Bank of England historical macroeconomic data was used to create the content of this file.

`Population.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

Crop data. *British agricultural production of arable crops (1270 – 1870).* The values listed are for wheat, rye, barley, oats, and pulses.

Sheet A3, Table 3.06 (English and British agricultural production (arable crops)) of Bank of England historical macroeconomic data was used to create the content of this file.

`Crop_total.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

Livestock data. *British agricultural production of livestock products (1270 – 1870).* The values listed are for milk, beef, veal, mutton, pork, wool, hides, and hay.

Sheet A3, Table 3.04 (English and British agricultural production (livestock products)) of Bank of England historical macroeconomic data was used to create the content of this file.

`Livestock.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

Industrial data. *British industrial production for key industries (1270 – 1870).* The values listed are for tin, iron, coal, wool/textiles, leather, foodstuffs, construction and printed books.

Sheet A4, Table 4.02 (English and British industrial production (key industries)) of Bank of England historical macroeconomic data was used to create the content of this file.

`Industrial.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

GDP(O) data. *British GDP(O) (1270 – 1870).* The values listed are for agriculture, industry, services and GDP.

Sheet A6 and Sheet A7 (English and British GDP(O) (real GDP)) of Bank of England historical macroeconomic data was used to create the content of this file.

`GDP.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

Trade data. *Regional trade (1665 – 2015).* The values listed are for export/import of goods to/from Europe, Africa, Asia, North America including West Indies to 1972, South and Central America, and Australia.

Sheet A52, Column F (Regional trade shares (export/import of goods to/from regions)) of Bank of England historical macroeconomic data was used to create the content of this file.

`trade.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

Slave-related data. *A collection of geographic, imputed voyage and other data drawn from libraries and archives around the Atlantic world on the trans-Atlantic slave trade.* The original (re)source is the Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database. It contains an estimate of the number of captives transported between major sites in the Atlantic rim (1501 – 1866) – places where slaves embarked and disembarked. This quantity is a proxy for an external workforce; the values shown are underestimates of this labour force because the numbers exclude people from the dominions, colonies, protectorates, mandates and other territories ruled or administered by Britain. These estimates were used to create the content of this file.

`Slaves.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

British colonialism-related data. *The year a former colony or dominion gained its independence from Britain.*

The original (re)source is

Wikipedia: List of countries that have gained independence from the United Kingdom.

Material in the Wikipedia entry was used to create the content of this file.

`Colonies_indep_full_copy.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

European colonialism-related data. *Possessions and colonies of European countries: Belgium, France, Italy, Portugal, Spain, the Netherlands, UK, or another country.*

The original (re)sources are

Wikipedia: Belgian colonial empire

Wikipedia: French possessions and colonies

Wikipedia: Italian colonies

Wikipedia: Portuguese colonies

Wikipedia: Spanish colonies

Wikipedia: Dutch colonies

Wikipedia: List of countries that have gained independence from the UK

Wikipedia: sovereign states

Material in these Wikipedia entries was used to create the content of this file.

`european_colonies.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

UK interest rates. *Interest rates set by the Bank of England (central bank of the UK).*

Sheet A31 (Interest rates set by the Bank of England) of Bank of England historical macroeconomic data was used to create the content of this file.

`interest_rates.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

USA interest rates. *Interest rates set by the Federal Reserve System (central bank of the USA).*

The original (re)source is

H.15 Selected Interest Rates.

The “Federal funds effective rate” 1954 – 2017 was used to create the content of this file.

Federal_interest_rates.csv (TEXT file: table of data)

Agricultural production and global land acquisitions. *Economic contribution of agricultural sector to GDP (average percent) for 28 countries that have been the targets of significant large-scale land acquisitions and all other countries (1980 – 2010).*

The original (re)source is

Figure 1 of Land grabbing: a preliminary quantification of economic impacts on rural livelihoods and contains data for Angola, Argentina, Benin, Brazil, Cameroon, Colombia, Congo, DRC, Ethiopia, Gabon, Ghana, Guatemala, Indonesia, Liberia, Madagascar, Malaysia, Morocco, Mozambique, Nigeria, Papua New Guinea, Peru, Philippines, Russia, Sierra Leone, South Sudan and Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda, and Uruguay. The spreadsheet provided by Kyle F. Davis, lead author of this paper, was used to create the content of this file.

Figure_1_data_Kyle_transposed.csv (XLS file: table of data)

KyleDavisFigure1data.xlsx (XLS file: spreadsheet from K.F. Davis)

Historical and operative trade agreements. *International and multi-lateral free trade agreements.*

The original (re)source are

International trade agreement arising from the Asian-African Conference of Bandung

Wikipedia: operating multi-lateral free-trade agreements.

Material in these (re)sources was used to create the content of this file. It contains information for Bandung (Asian-African Conference of Bandung), EUCU (European Union Customs Union), EFTA (European Free Trade Association), AC (Andean Community), APTA (Asia-Pacific Trade Agreement), SADCFTA (Southern African Development Community Free Trade Area), GCC (Gulf Cooperation Council), MERCOSUR (Southern Common Market), CEFTA (Central European Free Trade Agreement), AFTA (ASEAN Free Trade Area), SICA (Central American Integration System), COMESA (Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa), EEA (European Economic Area), NAFTA (North American Free Trade Agreement), G-3 (G-3 Free Trade Agreement), IGA (International Grains Agreement), GAFTA (Greater Arab Free Trade Area), DR-CAFTA (Dominican Republic-Central America Free Trade Agreement), SAFTA (South Asian Free Trade Area), EAC (East African Community), AANZFTA (ASEAN-Australia-New Zealand Free Trade Area), CISFTA (Commonwealth of Independent States Free Trade Area), PAFTA (Pacific Alliance Free Trade Area), RCEP (Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership), and TPP (Trans-Pacific Partnership).

Trade_agreements.csv (TEXT file: table of data)

Global land acquisitions. *Percent of the land area of a country that has been acquired in transnational deals.*

The original (re)sources are

Land Matrix: transnational large-scale land acquisitions (size of land acquired in a country)

World Bank: World Development Indicators (size of a country).

Material in these (re)sources was used to create the content of this file.

pct_target.csv (TEXT file: table of data)

Global land acquisitions and UK/USA investors *Countries targetted by investors from the UK and the USA*

The original (re)sources are Land Matrix investor countries involved in transnational large-scale land acquisitions ordered by the

area acquired

number of deals.

Material in these (re)sources was used to create the content of this file.

`targetcountries.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

Impact of synthetic biology on natural products. *Countries where the traditional livelihoods of farmers, growers, pickers, harvesters and others as well as biodiversity are under threat because of the replacement of natural products by compounds produced using synthetic biology.*

The original (re)source is

Synthetic Biology, Biodiversity & Farmers.

This 2016 report considers 13 food, flavour, cosmetic and fragrance ingredients: agarwood, ambergris/Clary Sage, artemisinin, ginseng, patchouli, rose oil, saffron, sandalwood, shea, cocoa butter and CBEs, squalenes (olives), stevia, vanilla, and vetiver. For each of these 13 natural products, the case study lists the countries where it is produced (see “Hotspots” and “Also Grown In”). Material in the report was used to create the content of this file.

`natprods_countries.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

`etc_synbiocasestudies_2016.pdf` (PDF file: downloaded report)

Global O₂ levels. *O₂ levels at 9 stations across the world.*

The original (re)source is

Average daily O₂ concentration at 9 stations across the world (O₂/N₂ and APO level in per meg units). The stations and their 3-letter abbreviation are Alert, NWT, Canada (alt); Cold Bay, Alaska (cba); Cape Kumukahi, Hawaii (kum); La Jolla Pier, California (ljo); Mauna Loa Observatory, Hawaii (mlo); American Samoa (sam); Cape Grim, Australia (cgo); Palmer Station, Antarctica (psa); and South Pole (spo). A file `XXXoav2.csv` (XXX: 3-letter station identifier) contains the average and standard deviation of flask replicates at the specific station and time. The date (year, month, day) and mean value fields from the downloaded files were used to create the content of this file (the O₂ concentrations is the average of the 9 mean values).

`Global_O2average.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

Global CO₂ levels. *CO₂ levels at 9 locations across the world.*

The original (re)source is

Average daily CO₂ concentration at 9 stations across the world (CO₂ level in ppm)

See Global O₂ levels for details about how the content of this file was created.

`Global_CO2average.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

El Niño and La Niña episodes. *Warm (El Niño) and cold (La Niña) episodes (1950 – 2017).*

The original (re)source is

National Weather Service Climate Prediction Center, historical El Niño/La Niña episodes.

Material on this web page was used to create the content of this file.

`elnino_lanina.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

La Via Campesina (LVC). *Countries of residence of LVC member organisations.*

The original (re)source is

member Organisations of La Via Campesina

This international movement brings together over 200 million small scale producers. Material on this site was used to create the contents of this file.

`lvc_organisations.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

World Forum of Fish Harvesters and Fish Workers (WFF). *Countries of residence of WFF member organisations.*

The original (re)source is

member organisations of World Forum of Fish Harvesters and Fish Workers

This international body encompasses small scale fishers' organisations.
Material on this site was used to create the content of this file.

`wff_organisations.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

Globally Important Agricultural Heritage Systems (GIAHS) data. *Names and locations of GIAHS sites in Africa, Asia and the Pacific, Europe and Central Asia, Latin America and the Caribbean, and Near East and North Africa.*

The original (re)source is

GIAHS around the world

These sites have been created, shaped and maintained by generations of farmers and herders, are based on diverse natural resources, and use locally adapted management practices. Material provided by CleliaMaria Puzzo, Food and Agriculture Organisation, was used to create the content of this file.

`Coordinates_of_Designated_and_Potential_GIAHS_sites.xlsx` (XLS file: spreadsheet from C. Puzzo)

Centres of agricultural biodiversity *Location of 12 major centres of diversity of agricultural crops and livestock.*

The original (re)source is

Seed Map, an online portal for seeds, biodiversity and food

Material on this site was used to create the contents of this file.

`seedmap_cab.csv` (TEXT file: table of data)

Software used to create visualisations

All visualisations were produced using the R Project for Statistical Computing, a free software environment for statistical computing and graphics. The R libraries and packages used to create the timelines and events charts and cartograms are

- `xts`: eXtensible Time Series, “Provide for uniform handling of R’s different time-based data classes by extending `zoo`, maximizing native format information preservation and allowing for user level customization and extension, while simplifying cross-class interoperability”.
- `dygraphs`, “The `dygraphs` package is an R interface to the `dygraphs` JavaScript charting library. It provides rich facilities for charting time-series data in R”.
- `Leaflet`, “Leaflet is one of the most popular open-source JavaScript libraries for interactive maps”.
- `rworldmap`: Mapping global data, vector and raster, “Enables mapping of country level and gridded user datasets”.
- `RColorBrewer`: ColorBrewer Palette, “Provides color schemes for maps (and other graphics) designed by Cynthia Brewer”.
- `Classes and Methods for Spatial Data`, “Classes and methods for spatial data; the classes document where the spatial location information resides, for 2D or 3D data. Utility functions are provided, e.g. for plotting data as maps, spatial selection, as well as methods for retrieving coordinates, for subsetting, print, summary, etc.”
- `maptools`: Tools for Reading and Handling Spatial Objects. “Set of tools for manipulating and reading geographic data, in particular ESRI shapefiles; C code used from `shapelib`. It includes binary access to GSHHG shoreline files. The package also provides interface wrappers for exchanging spatial objects with packages such as `PBSmapping`, `spatstat`, `maps`, `RArcInfo`, `Stata tmap`, `WinBUGS`, `Mondrian`, and others.”